

Polyprenylated benzophenones from *Garcinia indica*

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Two polyprenylated benzophenones, viz. xanthochymol and isoxanthochymol have been isolated and identified from the stem bark of *Garcinia indica*. The high resolution mass spectra and antibacterial activity of these compounds are reported.

Garcinia indica (choiss) (Hindi : *kokam*; Marath : *amsol*) is a slender evergreen tree found in the tropical main forest of Western Ghats, India. Its fruit is anthelmintic and cardio-tonic¹. Euxanthone², Volkansiflavone², morelloflavone², garcinol³, isogarcinol³, β -sitosterol⁴, fatty acids^{4,5} and amino acids⁵ were reported from different parts of this plant. Now we report the isolation and identification of two polyprenylated benzophenones from the chloroform extract of the stem bark of *G. indica*.

Compound 1. m.p. 135°, C₃₈H₅₀O₆ (M⁺ m/z 602.3621), [α]_D = 0 (0.025, MeOH), gave green color with alcoholic ferric chloride and decolorized alkaline potassium permanganate. characteristic of catechol group and aliphatic double bonds, respectively. UV and IR spectra indicated xanthochymol structure and the high resolution mass spectrum and its fragmentation pattern confirmed that the compound is xanthochymol (1)^{3,6,7}. It gave a trimethyl ether, m.p. 110°, C₄₁H₅₆O₆ (M⁺ m/z 644.4045).

Further, compound 1 was thermally isomerized to isoxanthochymol (2)⁷. Compound 2 had m.p. 238°, C₃₈H₅₀O₆ (M⁺ m/z 602.36), [α]_D = 0 (0.027, MeOH). The physical, UV, IR, ¹H, ¹³C NMR, mass spectral data and mass spectral fragmentation of compound 2 are identical to those reported for isoxanthochymol (2)^{7,8}. It is the first report of isolation of (±)-xanthochymol and (±)isoxanthochymol from the stem bark of *G. indica* (choiss).

Preliminary investigations indicated that xanthochymol (1) possesses good antibacterial activity (paper disc method⁹) against *Staphylococcus aureus* at higher concentration (400 µg/ml) while moderate activity at lower concentrations (200, 100 and 50 µg/ml), but inactive against *Escherchia coli*.

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected.

G. indica (choiss) stem bark was procured from South Canara, India, during May 1992 and identified. Shade-dried and coarsely powdered stem bark (500 g) was extracted successively with pet. ether and methanol in cold. The methanol extract yielded a dark brown solid (9.0 g). This solid was successively extracted with chloroform and ethyl acetate. The chloroform extract was concentrated under reduced pressure to yield a semisolid (3.5 g) which upon maceration with hexane gave a yellow solid (3.0 g). It was chromatographed over silica gel (200 mesh) using pet. ether, pet. ether-ethyl acetate 9 : 1, 8 : 2, 7 : 3 and 1 : 1 (v/v) as eluents successively.

Compound (1) : Pet. ether-ethyl acetate (8 : 2, v/v) fractions yielded xanthochymol (1)⁷ (0.1 g), M⁺ m/z 602.3621 (3% C₃₈H₅₀O₆); 601.3509 (6, C₃₈H₄₉O₆); 464.2514 (20, C₂₈H₃₂O₆); 343.1156 (7, C₁₉H₁₉O₆); 341.1071 (37, C₁₉H₁₇O₆); 327.0898 (30, C₁₈H₁₅O₆); 311 (100); 69.0708 (30, C₆H₉). Compound 1 on methylation with dimethyl sulfate and potassium carbonate in dry acetone yielded a trimethyl ether derivative (3). High resolution mass spectrum : M⁺ m/z 644.4055 (3%, C₄₁H₅₆O₆); 507.2713 (12, C₃₁H₃₉O₆); 452.2162 (21, C₂₇H₃₂O₆); 438.2007 (20, C₂₆H₃₀O₆); 384.1594 (54, C₂₂H₂₄O₆), 370 (74); 353.0995 (63, C₂₀H₁₇O₆); 315.0834 (100, C₁₇H₁₅O₆); 165.0579 (15, C₉H₉O₃); 69.0710 (8, C₅H₉). Compound 1 on heating at 200° for 5 min and then purified by column chromatography yielded isoxanthochymol⁷.

Compound (2) : Pet. ether-ethyl acetate (7 : 3, v/v) fraction gave isoxanthochymol (2)^{7,8} (0.15 g).

Note

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